

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KANNEH****FIRST NAME: SHEKU****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 6-12)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 15)
3. American vs. British Writing Styles (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
6. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2024, 58-59)
7. Corrections to Papers

GOOD ACADEMIC WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

It has been a challenging start to the program. I am caught between excitement and confusion pursuing the Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Climate Change and Sustainability. This is my major exposure to an expressed online academic program. I have tried understanding the EUCLID modus operandi and expected responsibilities to deliver on the course. The task is heavy, and there are many documents to read. In extreme fear and panic, I hope my first response paper to the course instructor will be meaningful. Starting here, I have realized that learning is a continuous process that never ends until you are called my God.

Though I struggled with my health challenge, I managed to go through the introductory process, register and log into the LMS portal, install Zotero, download the necessary course pack for period 1, and watch the course videos. I have read the Course pack (**ACA-401/ACA-401D**) revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, 2024.

Writing a good essay is the foundation of the Ph.D. program. It underscores the rules for acceptable and professional writing. I have read instructions on language, use of paragraphs, headings, footnotes, citations, British vs American writing styles, etc. Most of the reading occurs to me as new learning, encouraging me to start going into the course with an open mind for new opportunities.

This response paper will focus on six key concepts I learned from the **ACA-401/ACA-401D** course pack for period one, the basic tutorials, and the student orientation handout. These include Essay Writing, Punctuation, American vs. British writing styles, Plagiarism, Latin Abbreviations and Expressions, and Corrections to papers.

2) GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

The chapter highlights the basics of essay writing and identifies two types of writing (“Fiction and nonfiction”). It guides the considerations on starting, researching the topic, organizing the idea, writing, referencing, and editing the essay (EUCLID 2024, 7).

I understand that academic writing is not a mere think-and-write process; it follows a rigorous approach to answering hypotheses and communicating ideas based on evidence. It must have some level of formality citations and references to other writers. This can only be achieved through reviews and analysis of different works or write-ups (EUCLID 2024, 7).

In starting an essay, a plan should be developed, and time should be assigned to research the topic you intend to write on adequately. The first step is to understand the topic. Reading and researching what to write is a critical next step, which gives the knowledge and evidence on what you already know about the topic, new learning, and locating the source of the useful material for the work. I have read that it is always important to structure your writing into three main parts (introduction, body, and conclusion) after selecting the information you will use to answer the questions the essay seeks (EUCLID 2024, 8-10).

I have noted from the thumb rules for writing that it is good to personalize ideas when writing an essay. Your critique and evidence-based argument are critical when you analyze the work of others. I understand that when writing, one should focus on the main thesis of your paper in the opening paragraph. I have noted that in writing, one should stay focused with careful thoughts and clear ideas (EUCLID 2024, 13-14).

3) THE USE OF PUNCTUATION

I have understood that punctuation marks are critical to enhancing the clarity of your writing. In this section, I have read about punctuation marks and their usage with examples, including the difference between bad and good punctuation. To avoid the issue of incorrect use, one must reduce the number of punctuations as much as possible as long as one can maintain the meaning of the sentence (EUCLID 2024, 16).

I have noted the use of different punctuation marks. I concur that apostrophe (') applications depend on the circumstance. For example, in the case of possession, the use of its application for singular nouns is different from that of plural nouns. For singular nouns, the apostrophe mark comes before the s (e.g., Sheku's laptop). In plural nouns, the apostrophe comes immediately after the s (e.g., the builders' safety wear). Do not use an apostrophe to make a plural, even with a word/phrase that is not usually written in the plural or appears clunky. The following examples take an s as normal in English to make their plurals (EUCLID 2024, 16).

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH WRITING STYLES

American and British English are the most popular official English used worldwide. I have noted that American English has grown with dominant influence worldwide because of foreign policy, innovations, and openness (EUCLID 2024, 25).

Before now, I had paid less attention to the differences and similarities between American and British English. In most cases, I have unconsciously used both simultaneously in writing (particularly the spelling). However, reading the course pack, I have noted some differences in as much as they are similar to the greater extent. The divergence is attributed to national history and culture. They are shown in pronunciation, spelling, additional meaning, and writing style. I have also noted that American and British English cannot be used simultaneously in professional writing. You have to decide on one of the two, and it should flow throughout your writing (EUCLID 2024, 24-32).

5) PLAGIARISM

In the fourth chapter of the course pack, I read about plagiarism and how to avoid it. I have noted that it is vital to avoid plagiarism while writing papers. Plagiarism is the uncredited use of an idea or word in your writing. I have noted that copying and pasting from the internet using the words or ideas of other writers, paraphrasing, and not giving credit to the author is unethical and demonstrates dishonesty as a professional (EUCLID 2024, 34).

I agree that plagiarism can be avoided by properly citing the author or source of the information you have used. In citation, one needs to be aware of the in-text citation (citing the piece of work you are using within the actual text itself) and the list of works cited. The most common things to cite are the exact words of an author or ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but written in your own words (EUCLID 2024, 34-36).

6) STYLE GUIDE

I have noted that creative writers intentionally avoid needing a style guide, believing that the ability to follow a standard English writing style should be part of every writer. However, a style guide creates a means of documenting basic rules or features of writing that allow writers to ensure consistency in writing output. Because each writing has its targeted audience, it is important to note that the style guide for a particular audience should ensure that the information provided is in acceptable form and consistent with previous publications that the audience already has (EUCLID 2024, 41).

7) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

I have noted the common Latin abbreviations and their use. Latin abbreviations have recently become commonly used in writing. I have understood that they are more appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing. Terms like e.g. (exempli gratia) and i.e. (id est) are common in writing, helping to explain examples or definitions clearly. I have, however, noted that in formal, business, and technical writing, it is necessary to use the English equivalent of the abbreviation for readers to understand the meaning of your essay clearly. Using plain language in writing is the best because it is simple and direct. I know that using short sentences with simple words is good when writing in plain language, but also avoiding jargon, acronyms, and abbreviations (EUCLID 2024, 58-64).

8) CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

I have noted how instructors correct papers and give feedback. Track changes and comments are the major tools in the MS Word toolbar for making corrections. Where the instructor intends to change or delete a word, sentence, or paragraph, it will be done in track changes so the writer can see what has been changed. If the instructor provides feedback on a particular word, sentence, or paragraph, it will be done through the comment (EUCLID 2024, 65-71).

9) CONCLUSION

RP 1 has been a challenging start for me. At the beginning of the journey to acquire the Doctor of Climate Change and Sustainability (DCCS), it is an exciting experience to read the course pack and the orientation documents, including watching the video tutorials. They have energized me but also pushed me to the realization that there is much to learn, including the additional efforts required to complete the course. I have gained a lot of new knowledge that will guide my writing throughout the course and beyond.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

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